

STORY TEACHING METHODOLOGY IN PRIMARY CLASSES**Olimov Khurshidjon Yunusaliyevich**

junior teacher Kokand State pedagogical institue

M.Adhamova**M.Bahodirova****M.Rustamov****Sh.Rahimov**

students of the Faculty of History of the KSPI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10430237>

Annotation: This article is discussed the words of wisdom mentioned in the 3 grade reading textbook. The use of wise words in education, students in primary education, in raising their worldview gives good results.

Key words: story, method, education, efficiency of knowledge.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinflarda hikoya o'qitish metodikasi umumiy xususiyatlari predmeti o'quvchilarga o'zbek tilini o'rgatish yo'llari va vositalari ya'ni nutqni o'stirish, o'qish va yozishni, o'zlashtirib olish to'g'risida fikr yuritigan.

Kalit so'zlar: Hikoya, metod, ta'lim-tarbiya, bilim samaradorligi.

Аннотация: В этой статье обсуждаются слова мудрость упомянутые в учебнике чтения для 4-классов. Использование мудрость слов обучении учащихся начальной школы в повышении их мировоззрения дает хорошие результаты.

Ключевые слова: История, метод, образование, эффективность знаний.

A story is a small artistic work, in which a certain event in a person's life, important aspects of life are summarized. A story often describes an episode in a person's life. Its content is more vital than that of a fairy tale". The content of the story is a suitable genre for elementary school students. Younger students are more interested in stories about the hero's behavior, appearance, portrait, and events. Therefore, introducing the child to the story is connected with the explanation of its plot. etc. are the main types of work. The content of the story is usually analyzed based on questions. Questions are used for two purposes: to analyze the content of the story and to compare evidence, opinions, conclusions, to determine and summarize the connections between events, actions In the lesson of reading a story, it is also important to explain the meaning of words and phrases that the students do not understand, otherwise they will not be able to understand the content of the story. Analyzing the content of the story and developing the students' speech on this basis takes a central place in reading the

story. After reading the story, students should be given time to prepare for thinking and expressing their opinions. The purpose of the first questions asked in relation to the read work is to find out whether the children liked the story or not, which character in it affected the character of the child. Only after that, questions are used that help to reveal the subject of the story, the direction of the story, to understand the character of the characters, and finally to find out the main idea of the work. types of work should not be neglected. Texts of the fairy tale genre attract the child with their charm. But the narrative genre is also unique in its vitality. Events in the story develop quickly. It describes a person's life and life scenes related to it. Students are interested in the character of the characters, their characteristics. For example, in the 3rd grade reading book "The sea my father built" (Hakim Nazir), "Alma" (Malik Muradov), "Ilmli minyashar" (Nurmat Maqsudi), "Khazonchinak" (O'. Hoshimov), "Kashterak" (A. Irisov), "Working girl" (Oybek) and other interesting stories are given. They are diverse in terms of subject matter and differ in the character traits of their heroes. The story is related to a certain period. Students, due to their interest in the spirituality of the heroes, can see the light of life. and dark sides. They develop love for beauty and elegance, and hatred for evil during reading and analyzing stories. For example, in the 3rd grade, in the story "Jalaluddin Manguberdi", Genghis Khan and hatred for his troops is aroused, in the example of the behavior of Jalaluddin Manguberdi, love for the Motherland is aroused, through his fate, a sense of pride for his ancestors appears. The analysis of the story as a literary genre requires to work on the basis of its specific characteristics and function. Every word, phrase, sentence in it serves to express the writer's opinion. The text of the story should be a source not only for studying its content or artistic features, but also for the use of expressive, literary, conditional or creative reading, problematic methods of analysis. In elementary grades, various analyzes are conducted on the study of the subject, composition, characters of the story based on the work on the text. In this, the student's creative activity increases, the range of creative thinking expands. The following activities are carried out on the basis of the text to master the content of the story: 1. Answering the teacher's questions about the content of the text. 2. Completing a quiz based on the text of the story. 3. Pupils make questions about the content of the story. 4. Draw pictures suitable for the story. 5. Divide the text of the story into parts. 6. Find a title for each part. 7. Plan the story. 8. Planned retelling (full, abbreviated and creative retelling). 9. Writing a narrative based on a plan. A story is a small artistic work, in which a certain event in a

person's life, important aspects of life are summarized. A story often describes an episode in a person's life. Its content is more vital than that of a fairy tale". The story is a suitable genre for elementary school students. Younger students are more interested in stories about the hero's behavior, appearance, portrait, and events. That's why introducing a child to a story is related to the explanation of its subject. is one of the main types of work. The content of the story is usually analyzed on the basis of questions. Questions are used for two purposes: to analyze the content of the story and to compare evidence, opinions, conclusions, to determine and generalize the connection between events and actions. In the lesson of reading a story, it is also important to explain the meaning of words and phrases that the students do not understand, otherwise they will not be able to understand the content of the story. Analyzing the content of the story and developing the students' speech on this basis takes a central place in reading the story. After reading the story, students should be given time to prepare for thinking and expressing their opinions. The purpose of the first questions asked about the read work is to find out whether the children liked the story or not, which character in it influenced the child. Only after that, questions are used that help to reveal the plot of the story, the direction of the story, to understand the character of the characters, and finally to find out the main idea of the work. When analyzing a work of art, it is important to fully explain the subject, and should not neglect such tasks as describing the characters, analyzing the structure of the work, and analyzing the language. Texts typical of the fairy tale genre attract children with their charm. But the narrative genre is also unique in its vitality. Events in the story develop quickly. It describes a person's life and life scenes related to it. Students are interested in the character of the hero, their characteristics. For example, the sea built by my father (Hakim Nazir), "Alma (Malik Muradov), "Ilmli minyashar" (Nurmat Maqsudiy), Khazonchinak (O'. Hoshimov), Q oshterak (A. Irisov), "Worker" in the 3rd grade reading book girl (Oybek) and other interesting stories are given. They are diverse in subject matter and differ in the character traits of their characters. The story is related to a certain era. Due to the interest of the students in the spirituality of the characters, the life of they begin to have a certain understanding of the bright and dark sides. They develop love for beauty and sophistication, and hatred for evil during familiarization with stories and their analysis. For example, Jalaluddin Manguberdi in the 3rd grade." if the story evokes hatred towards Genghis Khan and his troops, the example of Jalaluddin Manguberdi's behavior evokes love for the motherland, and through his fate, a feeling of pride in his

ancestors appears. Narrative analysis as a literary genre requires work based on its own characteristics and task. Every word, phrase, sentence in it serves to express the writer's opinion. The text of the story should be a source not only for studying its content or artistic features, but also for the use of expressive, literary, conditional or creative reading, problematic methods of analysis. In elementary grades, various analyzes are conducted on the study of the plot, composition, and characters of the story based on work on the text. In this, the student's creative activity increases, the range of creative thinking expands. Studying and analyzing the characters of Jalaluddin Manguberdi's story, their behavior, can be done based on the following plan based on the text:

1. Finding the place where Genghis Khan used a trick in the text. To find out what impression it made on the students.
2. Find and read the place where Jalaluddin Manguberdi's victory against the Mongols in Iran and Afghanistan is described.
3. To find out what happened as a result of the distribution of booty by the commanders. Find this place in the text.
4. To determine where Jalaluddin Manguberdi's bravery was seen.
5. To tell why Genghis Khan confessed to Jalaluddin Manguberdi.

After that, students will think about Jalaluddin Manguberdi. They compare and contrast the actions of Genghis Khan and Jalaluddin Manguberdi. On the basis of the text, the following works are carried out to master the content of the story:

1. Answering the teacher's questions about the content of the text.
2. Completing a quiz based on the text of the story.
3. Pupils make questions about the content of the story.
4. Draw pictures suitable for the content of the story.
5. Dividing the text of the story into parts.
6. Find a title for each part.
7. Plan the story.
8. Planned retelling (full, abbreviated and creative retelling).
9. Writing a statement based on the plan.

The comprehensibility of the text of the story being read is crucial in the analysis. Comprehensibility refers to the uniqueness of the artistic world created by the writer, the compatibility of the image with the student's life experience and level of knowledge. When learning a story, questions are usually asked by the teacher, but it is very useful to ask students questions about the content of the work and the behavior of the characters involved. This method is very

pleasing to children and enlivens the work, helps students to better understand the content of the work, to acquire the skill of coherent expression of their thoughts, to fully remember the connection between the content and the events. The lesson of interpreting the story can be conducted on the basis of the following plan: 1. Preparing the story for reading (characterizing people's lives and times as in the story, etc.). 2. Reading a story (in which a complete and meaningful part can be read expressively by the teacher or a pre-prepared student). 3. Work on vocabulary. 4. Examination of perception (brief discussion on the behavior of participants, relationships between people and events, artistic means). 5. Re-reading the story (teaching students in parts and roles). 6. Arranging a conversation about each section (part) of the story, creating a story plan. 7. Planned retelling. 8. Creative and independent works based on the story. 9. Preparation for expressive reading or acting out of the story (in class or at home). 10. Expressive flow of the story and expressive retelling.

References:

1. I.A. Karimov A perfect generation - the foundation of the development of Uzbekistan T. "Sharq", 1997, page 5;
2. Yu.K.Babansky "Methods of reading in modern secondary schools" Tashkent-"Teacher" 1990.
3. T. Gaffarova, E Shodmonov, Kh. Gulomova" "mother tongue" textbook, Tashkent. 2019, page 65.
- 4.M. Umarov, Kh. Umrakulova, R. Tojiboyeva textbook for 3rd grade Tashkent 2019.
5. Mahmudov M. Organization of problem learning at school" Tashkent-"Teacher" 1981
6. www.ziyo.uz.com library

